

Inhibition of stainless steel by use of thiourea derivative as inhibitors in 20% HCl

Rajesh Kumar Singh, S. Prakash, S. K. Singh and D. Prakash*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005, Bihar, India

Manuscript received 11 December 2007, revised 19 February 2008, accepted 15 April 2008

Abstract : The stainless steel is very important material for petroleum industry and it is used in several processing units like oil recovery, refining of crude oil, transportation, storage and petroleum products. The corrosion inhibitors are used to reduce corrosion damage in sub-surface equipments in both oil and gas well. For this work inhibition activity is studied by use of inhibitors, *N,N'*-di-*o*-tolylthiourea, *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea and *N*-phenylthiourea and experimental work can be done by gravimetric method and potentiostatic polarization at different temperature in 20% HCl solution.

Keywords : Stainless steel, inhibitors, gravimetric, potentiostatic polarization.

Introduction

Stainless steel used for petroleum production operations are carried out under a variety of hostile environment to enhance oil recovery. In this investigation *N,N'*-di-*o*-tolylthiourea, *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea and *N*-phenylthiourea are taken as inhibitors to study the corrosion of stainless steel in 20% HCl and its inhibition phenomena¹. A majority of corrosion inhibitors used in petroleum industries are nitrogen and sulphur containing organic compounds² which are highly effective at high temperature to control corrosion of oil well reservoir stimulation³. Nitrogen containing inhibitors have been reported to be effective in H₂S containing media and it is suggested that amine corrosion inhibitors interact with iron sulphide corrosion product layer to form surface complex⁴, whereas amine and nitrogen containing heterocyclic compounds had been studied extensively inhibitors for sour corrosive media⁵. The effect of heterocyclic organic compounds and other organic compounds containing nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen such as amines and several Schiff bases on corrosion of steel in the acidic solutions has been investigated by several workers⁶.

Results and discussion

Effect of concentration : The effect of concentration of inhibitors on the corrosion of stainless steel in 20% HCl is depicted in Table 1. It is observed that when the concentration of inhibitors is increased, the inhibition efficiency also gets increased. The inhibition efficiencies range from 65 to 92% with *N,N'*-di-*o*-tolylthiourea, 57 to 94% with *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea and 56 to 95% with *N*-

phenylthiourea. It can be seen from the Table 1 that all these three inhibitors are effective inhibitors especially at concentration 5 mM and above. The biggest inhibition efficiency (IE) of 95% is given by *N*-phenylthiourea at 10 mM concentration and *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea give 94% at the same concentration. In case of these two compounds there is a sharp enhancement in inhibitors efficiencies on increasing the concentration from 1 mM to 10 mM. The plots of IE (%) vs *C* (inhibitors concentration) and log ($\theta/1 - \theta$) (θ = surface coverage) vs log *C* are straight line with different concentrations of inhibitors in 20% HCl solution at 30 °C.

Table 1. Inhibition of stainless steel by different concentration in 20% HCl at 30 °C

Inhibitors	<i>C</i> (mM)	<i>K</i> (mmpy)	log ($\theta/1 - \theta$)	IE (%)
IH (i)	0.0	0.088	0.00	00.0
IH (ii)	1.0	0.030	0.63	65
	5.0	0.010	0.76	88
	10.0	0.007	0.91	92
	1.0	0.037	0.92	57
IH (iii)	5.0	0.026	1.05	70
	10.0	0.005	1.18	94
	1.0	0.038	0.78	56
	5.0	0.027	0.92	69
	10.0	0.004	1.05	95

Effect of temperature : Table 2 gives the results of the immersion tests in the presence of 5 mM of different

inhibitors at five different temperatures 30, 40, 50, 60 and 70 °C. Increasing the temperature from 30 to 70 °C without inhibitors enhance the corrosion rate from 0.088 to 1.120 mmpy, about 13 times and in presence of inhibitors the trends are seen to be different in many cases. In the case of *N,N'*-di-*o*-tolythiourea and *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea the corrosion rate actually decreases on going from 30 to 40 °C and then show an increasing trend. The inhibition efficiency increases from 88 to 96% with *N,N'*-di-*o*-tolythiourea, 70 to 97% with *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea and 71 to 95% with *N*-phenylthiourea respectively on going from 30 to 70 °C. Thiourea derivatives form complex with metal ions and multiples points of attachment to metal surface to protect the metal from corrosion. In some cases complex formation takes place at higher temperature. The plots of $\log K$ vs $1/T$, $\log (\theta/1 - \theta)$ vs $1/T$ and IE (%) vs T are straight line in 20% HCl.

Table 2. Inhibition of stainless steel by 5 mM concentration of different inhibitors in 20% HCl at different temperature

Inhibitors	Temp.	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	70 °C
IH (i)	K_0	0.088	0.186	0.207	0.925	1.120
	K	0.010	0.009	0.021	0.037	0.038
	IE (%)	88	95	89	90	96
	θ	0.88	0.95	0.89	0.90	0.96
IH (ii)	K_0	0.088	0.186	0.207	0.925	1.120
	K	0.026	0.006	0.022	0.021	0.027
	IE (%)	70	93	88	95	97
	θ	0.70	0.93	0.88	0.95	0.97
IH (iii)	K_0	0.088	0.186	0.207	0.925	1.120
	K	0.027	0.031	0.027	0.037	0.041
	IE (%)	71	83	86	96	95
	θ	0.71	0.83	0.86	0.96	0.95

The value of activation energies are given in Table 3. It can be seen that the activation energy of the corrosion reaction of stainless steel in HCl increases in the presence of inhibitors. The activation energy without inhibitor is found to be 10.98 kJ mol⁻¹ and it increases with the addition of inhibitors as shown in Table 3. The activation energy of the corrosion of stainless steel in the presence of inhibitors are higher with *N,N'*-di-*o*-tolythiourea and

N,N'-diphenylthiourea and lower with *N*-phenylthiourea. The order of activation energies in case of these inhibitors is IH (i) > IH (ii) > IH (iii).

The values of heat of adsorption are mention in Table 3. Obviously a higher value of adsorption shows a stronger adsorption and hence a better inhibition. The values of heat of adsorption for these compounds range from 22.96 to 36.36 kJ mol⁻¹ of which *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea and *N*-phenylthiourea show the maximum heat of adsorption. In the case of *N,N'*-di-*o*-tolythiourea, heat of adsorption is found to be low, 22.96 kJ mol⁻¹. The values of enthalpy, free energy and entropy are given in Table 3. It is observed that the values of enthalpy, free energy and entropy are negative and this indicates that strong adsorption takes place on metal surface. The thermal values of all the three inhibitors are very high so these inhibitors adsorb more strongly and form strong complex with metal⁷. The order of values for ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are IH (i) > IH (ii) > IH (iii).

Potentiostatic polarization : The cathodic and anodic total slopes for potentiostatic polarization curves have increased on the addition of inhibitors indicated in Table 4 and Fig. 1 interfering in both anodic and cathodic processes of the corrosion reaction. It is observed that all the three inhibitors have produced parallel displacement of both cathodic and anodic Tafel lines to more negative or positive values relative to the ones produced in the absence of inhibitors. This indicates that these inhibitors behave as mixed type inhibitors and that inhibition takes place by adsorption on metal surface. The values of corrosion current density and corrosion rates decrease with addition of inhibitors. The enhancement of inhibition efficiency with increase in inhibitor concentration supports the adsorption mechanism for inhibition⁸. The value of inhibition efficiency show that *N*-phenylthiourea has the lowest inhibitive effect followed by *N,N'*-di-*o*-tolythiourea and *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea has the highest inhibition effect.

Mechanism of inhibitors : The three nitrogen containing inhibitors have shown good inhibition for stainless steel in 20% HCl. Adsorption of thiourea and *N*-substituted thiourea occur through Fe-S interactions⁹. In strong

Table 3. Thermodynamical parameters of different inhibitors for stainless steel in 20% HCl

Inhibitors	Q (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔE (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)
IH (0)	-22.50	10.98	-20.29	-97.29	-21.87
IH (i)	-22.96	25.85	-23.79	-212.98	-43.17
IH (ii)	-36.36	21.05	-21.88	-194.04	-37.45
IH (iii)	-24.88	17.22	-18.05	-157.65	-33.81

Fig. 1. Polarization curves for stainless steel in 20% in the presence of various inhibitors.

Table 4. Potentiostatic polarization of different inhibitors for stainless steel in 20% HCl at 5 mM inhibitor concentration

Inhibitors	β_c (mV)	β_a (mV)	I_{corr} (μA)	IH (%)
IH (0)	0.50	0.48	10.0	00.0
IH (i)	0.75	0.72	5.5	81
IH (ii)	0.80	0.81	6.0	66
IH (iii)	0.79	0.78	6.5	53

acidic solution, the nitrogen may be protonated. The metal inhibitor bond is basically through S-atoms and the nitrogen groups, which are hydrophilic points towards the solution side. The difference in the inhibition efficiencies of these compounds are basically due to the different *N*-substituent groups the orientation of which affect the in-

hibition efficiencies of the compounds.

Experimental

The experiment was performed to study the inhibition effect of some organic compounds with nitrogen, sulphur and phenyl groups on stainless steel in 20% HCl. The corrosion rate was determined by gravimetric method and potentiostatic polarization equipments. Stainless steel coupons (3 cm × 2.5 cm × 0.5 cm) were ruffed with emery paper of increasing fineness and then washed with double distilled water and finally degreased with acetone and dried in air. The test solution was prepared with required amount of A.R. grade HCl to double distilled water and for each test 400 ml solution were taken in 500 ml bea-

kers. The requisite amounts of inhibitors were added to this solution before the tests. Stainless steel type 316 was used for the test. Potentiostatic polarization studies were carried out using an EG & G Princeton Applied Research Model 173 Potentiostat. A platinum electrode was used as an auxiliary electrode and a calomel electrode was used as reference electrode. The values of corrosion rate parameters are as follows : inhibitor (K), without inhibitor (K_0), inhibition efficiency (IE%), surface coverage (θ), heat of activation (ΔE), heat of adsorption (Q), enthalpy (ΔH), free energy (ΔG) and entropy (ΔS) at different concentration and same temperature and same concentration and different temperature. The corrosion rate (K), inhibition efficiency (IE%), surface coverage (θ), heat of activation (ΔE), heat of adsorption (Q), enthalpy (ΔH), free energy (ΔG), entropy (ΔS) and potentiostatic polarization were calculated using the following equations. The weight loss of test specimens after a known period of immersion rate in millimeter per year (mmpy) was calculated by the equation :

$$K = 13.56 W/DAt \quad (1)$$

where W = weight loss of test coupon expressed in kg, A = area of test coupon in square meter, D = density of the material in kg. M^{-3} , K = corrosion rate in millimeter per year (mmpy), t = time of exposure in hours.

The inhibition efficiency can be calculated from the corrosion rates using the expression :

$$IE (\%) = (1 - K/K_0) \quad (2)$$

where K is the corrosion rate with inhibitor and K_0 is the corrosion rate without inhibitor.

The surface coverage area may be written as :

$$\theta = (1 - K/K_0) \quad (3)$$

where θ = surface area, K = corrosion rate with inhibitor, K_0 = corrosion rate without inhibitor.

The activation energy was determined by Arrhenius equation :

$$d/dt (\log K) = \Delta E/RT^2 \quad (4)$$

where T is temperature in Kelvin and ΔE is the activation energy of the reaction.

Heat of adsorption was determined by Langmuir adsorption isotherm

$$\log (\theta/1 - \theta) = A.C \log (Q/RT) \quad (5)$$

Activation parameters were calculated by transition state

equation :

$$K = RT/Nh \log (\Delta S^\ddagger/R) \log (-\Delta H^\ddagger/RT) \quad (6)$$

where N is Avogadro's constant, h is Planck's constant, ΔS^\ddagger is the change of entropy activation and ΔH^\ddagger is the change of enthalpy activation.

The free energy of activation was calculated by

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger - T\Delta S^\ddagger \quad (7)$$

where ΔG^\ddagger free energy of activation.

The metal penetration rate (mmpy) was determined by

$$C.R \text{ (mmpy)} = 0.1288 I_{\text{corr}} \text{ (mA/cm}^2\text{)} \times Eq.Wt \text{ (g)} / \rho \text{ (g/cm}^3\text{)} \quad (8)$$

where I_{corr} is the corrosion current density, ρ is specimen density and $Eq.Wt$ is specimen weight.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Department of Chemistry, Patna University, the Department of Applied Chemistry, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad for providing laboratory facility and UGC for providing the financial support for this work.

References

1. D. Prakash, Rajesh Kumar Singh, G. Udayabhanu and Ranju Kumari, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2006, **22**, 257.
2. D. Prakash, Rajesh Kumar Singh and Ranju Kumari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 1256.
3. A. Jayaraman and R. C. Saxena, *Corrosion/96*, Paper No. 221, NACE, 1996; D. Prakash, Rajesh Kumar Singh and Ranju Kumari, *Ind. J. Chem. Tech.*, 2006, **13**, 1555.
4. V. S. Sastri and J. R. Perumareddi, *Corrosion*, 1994, **50**, 56.
5. H. Okada and K. Suzuki, *Proc. 8th Int. Cong. Met. Corrosion*, DECHEMA, Germany, 1981, 1495; K. Suzuki, T. Kouno, E. Sato and T. Murata, *Corrosion*, 1982, **38**, 384; E. D. Burger and G. R. Chesnut, *Mater. Perform.*, 1982, **31**, 40.
6. S. Bilgie and N. Caliskan, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 2001, **31**, 79; M. A. Quraishi, M. A. W. Khan, M. Ajmal and S. V. K. Iyer, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 1996, **26**, 1253; M. N. Desai, M. B. Desai, C. B. Shah and S. M. Desai, *Corrosion Sci.*, 1996, **26**, 827.
7. G. C. Makovei and V. R. Koroleva, *Metal*, 1984, **6**, 978.
8. T. Savov and Simeonov, *Metallic Corrosion*, 8th Int. Conf. Metallic Corrosion, 1981, Vol. II, Mainz, Germany, 6-11 September, 1981.
9. K. Chandrasekhara Pillai and R. Narayan, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1976, **125**, 1393.